

Strategic Public Relations and Productivity of Teachers in the Digos City Division

Abdul Gapor M. De Guzman

Abstract. This study aimed to determine the relationship between public relations and the productivity of teachers in the Digos City Division. It employed descriptive-correlational research with the division's five (5) large-sized schools. This study was administered to 5 public schools and 120 teachers. The teachers have a high public relationship with the parents, community, teaching staff, and students. The teachers have a high level of productivity in physical activities, grants or aids, staff management, and the learning environment. A significant positive linear relationship was found between the public relation of teachers and productivity variables. The extent of public relations between teachers, stakeholders, parents, community, and teaching staff was extensive. The extent of productivity of teachers in terms of physical, grants or aids, staff management, and learning environment obtained a mean rating of 4.11 with a standard deviation of 0.76, which was described as extensive. There was a relationship between public relations and the productivity of teachers; a correlation coefficient r of 0.905 denotes a solid positive linear relationship, which means that the level of public relations of school heads caused 82 percent of the positive variation in the productivity level of teachers. Results indicated that there was sufficient evidence to reject the null hypothesis. Thus, there was a significant relationship between the two variables.

KEY WORDS

1. public relations 2. productivity 3. teachers

1. Introduction

Public relations, a strategic communication tool, plays a crucial role in disseminating information about individuals, groups, corporations, government agencies, and non-profits to the public. In the context of school districts, public relations serve as a conduit for conveying pertinent and accurate information, fostering mutual collaboration and decision-making, and highlighting the benefits of the school to students and society. This process also serves to raise community awareness, making public relations a vital component of school district operations. Teachers are needed in an organization such as the academe. Indeed, a teacher also has a significant role in achieving school accomplishments and students' good performance, and the stakeholders also play a vital role in all the aspects that are needed for the teachers to hone their expertise in handling schools. Teachers play a pivotal leadership role in the overall running of the schools. They have multiple roles in this part of the world, such as being a leader on instructions, accounting officers, and human resource officers in the community and school

in general. Learning is voluntary for students, and students do not voluntarily give effort when they are attached to school (McDougall, 2007). According to Sun et al. (2019), the role of teachers is divided between the managerial aspects and the instructional role, in which the managerial aspects take up most of their time. In the process of carrying a teachers leadership role, a good working relationship is a must to reap several benefits like improved relationships with the people around them, increased motivation among teachers, and high productivity because teachers are more likely to go along with changes that teachers want to implement and become more innovative and creative. In the Philippines, Ancho et al. (2022) reported that many teachers have also manifested little preparation in exercising interpersonal relations with stakeholders, which is very evident in the whole system of running their own schools. The impact is negative because relations among the parents, teachers, and students have been distorted in some country schools. Interaction between teachers and administrations is particularly interesting, as it involves teachers' participation. In the school personnel, it should be the basis for a peaceful society. Whether they are involved in a family or neighborhood dispute or a lawsuit involving thousands of dollars, these processes should be considered. Human resources are among the most critical and valuable resources in an organization. Human resources (HR) can be defined as the most important resource for affecting production performance in organizations. Industrial relationships are about the relationship between an employee and management; hence, industrial progress is impossible without laborers' cooperation and harmonious relationships. Therefore, it is in the interest of all to create and maintain good relations between employees and employers (Saks, 2022). The Department of Education for a significant implementation of Republic Act No. 9155 on Governance of Basic Education Act of 2001, that stresses before the teacher is appointed into the position of a school head or a principal, he or she shall possess corresponding criteria plus a passer of a principal qualifying examination (Estacio et al. 2022). According to Shaturaev, (2021) Section 3 of the Republic Act states the purposes and objectives of the Act are the following: to provide the framework for the governance of primary education which shall set the general directions for educational policies and standards and establish authority, accountability and responsibility for achieving higher learning outcomes; to define the roles and responsibilities of, and provide resources to, the field offices which shall implement educational programs, projects and services in communities they serve; to make schools and learning centers the most important vehicle for the teaching and learning of national values and for developing in the Filipino learners' love of country and pride in its rich heritage; to ensure that schools and learning centers receive the kind of focused attention they deserve and that educational programs, projects. He added that services take into account the interests of all members of the community; to enable the schools and learning centers to reflect the values of the community by allowing teachers/learning facilitators and other staff to have the flexibility to serve the needs of all learners; to encourage local initiatives for the improvement of schools and learning centers and to provide the means by which these improvements may be achieved and sustained; and to establish schools and learning centers as facilities where schoolchildren are able to learn a range of core competencies prescribed for elementary and high school education programs or where the out-of-school youth and adult learners are provided alternative learning programs and receive accreditation for at least the equivalent of a high school education. The very purpose of this study was to examine and screen applicants for teachers in order to hire quality and qualified teachers to run a specific a school in terms

of public relation and productiveness on his or her given tasks. In Digos City Division, there are many teachers have a difficulty in dealing interpersonal relation to the stakeholders and many of them have poor skill in establishing a strong partnership due to a little knowledge, preparation and experience in the field. Furthermore, the multiple tasks given to the teachers in which public relation was less in priority, this study seeks to find how the public relation of the teachers related to the productivity and to determine the level of public relation of teachers and productivity of the public elementary schools.

1.1. Review of Related Literature—Public Relations of Teachers, Parents, and Community

Public relations in education involve building beneficial relationships between schools and their stakeholders, such as parents, community members, and teaching staff. Bossman (2022) highlights the importance of understanding the history, law, ethics, and international nature of public relations to enhance its role in organizations and society. Amelia et al. (2022) emphasize legislation and programs that engage parents in their children's education, fostering skills at home to support academic success.

Leonardo and Boas (2021) and Redding (2019) discuss the impact of race and ethnicity in educational settings. They note that students benefit academically and behaviorally from having teachers who share their racial or ethnic background. Muturi and Zhu (2019) suggest that exposure to diversity in public relations courses influences students' perceptions of racial and ethnic issues positively.

Teaching Staff and Professional Development

Effective school administration is critical for teacher performance and satisfaction. Affandi et al. (2019) identify teacher collaboration for learning improvement as a key factor in professional learning communities that positively

affect teacher performance. Farmer et al. (2019) and Daniel et al. (2019) stress the importance of positive peer relationships and community engagement in fostering a supportive learning environment.

Cansoy (2019) asserts that school culture, influenced by beliefs and attitudes, shapes educational practices. Best practices include personal mastery, team learning, and building a shared vision. Burdett (2022) discusses the challenges and benefits of site-based management, which relies on collaboration among teachers, administrators, and parents to address conflicts and improve school responsiveness to community needs.

Students and Academic Performance

Student success is linked to teacher quality and administrative practices. Welekwe et al. (2023) found that while teacher quality in Rivers State, Nigeria, is high, it does not significantly reflect in student performance due to inadequate teaching methods. Zhang et al. (2023) recommend integrating diverse cultural practices in learning activities to enhance student engagement and moral development.

Grivet et al. (2021) explore the relationship between transformational leadership in school administration and teacher job satisfaction. They find that effective leadership contributes to a positive school environment and better student outcomes.

Physical Facilities and Learning Environment

Adequate physical facilities and learning resources are crucial for academic success. Carnevale et al. (2023) and Onyemauche et al. (2022) highlight the need for modern instructional and recreational facilities to improve student performance. Gurr et al. (2022) emphasize the importance of effective supervision in managing the growing number of students and teachers, ensuring quality education delivery.

Fig. 1. Conceptual framework of the study

2. Methodology

This chapter presented the methods used in the study, which consisted of the research design, research respondents, research instrument, data gathering procedure, and data analysis. The purpose of this study was to determine the public relations and productivity of teachers in the public schools in Digos City Division.

2.1. Research Design—This study employed the descriptive-correlational method to determine the public relations and productivity of teachers in Digos City Division’s public elementary schools. Descriptive method of research according to Gay (2000) combines both descriptive and correlational designs. Descriptive research involves collecting data in order to test a hypothesis or answer questions concerning the status of the respondents in the study. Correlational research, on the other hand, attempts to determine whether and to what degree a relationship exists between two quantitative variables. The purpose of correlational research was to establish a relationship in making predictions. Relationships investigation typically studies several variables believed to be related to major and complex variables. This design involves determining information about variables and individuals. A survey study was employed to measure the existing phenomenon. Its scope covered the five (5) public elementary schools of Digos.

2.2. Research Respondents—The subjects of the study were the parents, community, students and teaching staff of the five (5) large-

sized public elementary schools of Digos as samples for this study. Since the study determined the public relations and productivity of the school heads, the point of reference in selecting the respondents, the respondents was public elementary school teachers regardless of the position they possess, parents, community, and students. To describe fully the present status of public relation and productivity of teachers in public elementary schools of Digos City Division, this study was concentrate on the descriptive-correlational and using the survey type of research. It was a surveyed type of research, as described by Fraenkel (2007), in which researchers are often interested in the opinions of a large group of people about a particular topic or issue. Information was collected from a group of people in order to describe some aspects of characteristics.

2.3. Research Instrument—A self-crafted survey questionnaire was formulated based on the data required by this study. Experts’ validation by the Advisory Committee was done during the proposal presentation. The questionnaire was composed of two sets of survey questionnaires in the form of a checklist used in

this study, and the study variables were incorporated to answer the identified problems. The first set of questionnaire was focused the independent variable, which is the public relation of the school heads. The indicators of this variable were incorporated in the crafting of questionnaire. The second set of survey questionnaire indicated the productivity of teachers in the elementary schools of Digos and the indicators are the following: physical facilities, grant and aid, staff learning environment. Scaling was used in the analysis of the public relation and productivity of teachers in elementary schools. Scaling was used in the analysis of the public relations and productivity of teachers to further check and validate the results of the study. Further, before the administration of the research instrument, pilot testing was done on selected respondents. The survey questionnaire for the pilot test was subjected to reliability testing to establish using the Internal Consistency Method. The most appropriate method to use since the test contains dichotomously scored items that the examinee either passes or fails in an item. The final copy of the research survey questionnaires was validated by the panel of experts for approval.

The final revisions were made by incorporating all the corrections, comments, and suggestions given by the experts before distribution and administration. The preliminary versions of the questionnaires were shown to the expert validators, who then provided feedback on each version. They were given a standardized assessment instrument that allowed them to score, remark on, and make ideas about the improvement and growth of the questionnaire. Both the findings of the validation and the preliminary version of the research instrument were given to the research adviser to get comments and recommendations from them. The elements that were unclear or confusing were taken out, and the ones that were lacking were bolstered and made better. The researcher was given the opportunity to complete the research instrument after having it returned to them following correction and improvement. The pilot testing was conducted in small-sized elementary schools, and the respondent's are not included in the research survey. Pilot testing is purposely conducted to establish the reliability and validity of the test instrument. The questionnaire is designed and modified to suit the needs of the respondents.

Scale, Descriptive Rating, and Interpretation of Strategic Public Relations Manifestation

Scale	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	The strategic public relations is always manifested.
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The strategic public relations is oftentimes manifested.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The strategic public relations is sometimes manifested.
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The strategic public relations is rarely manifested.
1.0 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The strategic public relations is not manifested.

2.4. *Data Gathering Procedure*—The researcher underwent the following steps and procedures in gathering the data for this study: Submitting a request for approval to carry out the research. The researcher sought approval from the thesis advisor and the Dean of the Gradu-

ate School at The Rizal Memorial College, Inc. before beginning his research on mentorship and teacher growth. Along with the letter of support, the researcher also submitted a formal request to the Schools Division of Digos City for permission to perform the study. In order to

Scale, Descriptive Rating, and Interpretation of Teacher Productivity Manifestation

Scale	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	The productivity of teachers and teachers is always manifested.
3.40 – 4.59	Extensive	The productivity of teachers and teachers is oftentimes manifested.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The productivity of teachers and teachers is sometimes manifested.
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The productivity of teachers and teachers is rarely manifested.
1.0 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The productivity of teachers and teachers is not manifested.

conduct his or her study, the researcher needed the approval of the school principle before getting started. Tasks involving the distribution and collection of questionnaires. After the questionnaire had been validated and reliability tested, the researcher discussed it in detail to the respondents, with the blessing of the SDS and the backing of the school administration. The researcher should observe the AITF health regulations when giving out survey surveys. Google

forms were used to manage the survey’s distribution and proper URLs were sent to the responders. The researcher collected all the returned questionnaires after each responder had thoughtfully and thoroughly answered all the questions. Data collection and tabulation. Data were collected and processed once the survey questionnaires were distributed and returned. Data needed for analysis and interpretation was gathered using the proper statistical methods.

2.5. *Data Analysis*—In the treatment of data, the following statistical procedures were employed: Mean. This was used to answer the first two objectives of the study. More specifically, it was used to describe teachers’ public relations and productivity. Pearson r. This statis-

tical tool was used to determine the significant relationship between strategic public relations and the productivity of teachers. Linear Regression. This statistical tool was used to determine the significant influence between strategic public relations and the productivity of teachers.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the discussions of the problems in this study. They are discussed thoroughly, analyzed, and interpreted under the following headings and sequence: To the extent of public relations of teachers with the stakeholders

Table 1 presents the data on the summary of teachers’ public relations. The overall mean of the data in this table is 3.63. The indicators are presented with the corresponding mean: parents (3.40), community (3.79), teaching staff (3.32), and students (4.02). All the indicators

have a mean descriptive equivalent of Extensive. The extensive mean rating in this study suggests that teachers’ public relations are oftentimes manifested which public relations grant school directs an opportunity to share pertinent and accurate information (through mutual col-

laborations and decision-making) on how the school is of benefit to not only the students but the society as well. The results depicted in Table 5 was supported by the idea of Zhang et al. (2023) pointed out that school manager should give a prompt attention to express problems of students, and provide integration of various beliefs, cultures, practices and traditions of the community in the learning activities. Furthermore, the students should strengthen genuine school spiritually regardless of religion, and initiates continuous development of modules and supplementary materials for drills and exercise of students. Finally, provide the students a value reorientation programs for the school, on moral development and spiritual development. And agreed by Dinie (2016) stated that the factors causing teacher and school leaders conflicts in secondary schools of Wolaita zone. The study also aimed to discover the views of teachers and school leaders concerning the nature of conflicts, major causes, and types of conflicts, ways of conflict management, and roles of school leaders in conflict management. The findings of the study revealed that inappropriate reward sys-

tem, poor performance, evaluation system, communication problems and barriers, bad working conditions, lacks of participative decision making, inappropriate distribution of tasks and task overload, lack of professional commitment and lack of solving problems through the practice of table discussion are the major causes of conflict which took the highest magnitude for the expansion of conflict between teachers and school leaders in secondary schools. Fullan (2020) examines educational decentralization efforts in both developed countries, guided by two questions: first is under what conditions does school-based management (SBM) produce best results and the second is what are the roles and relationships of the school and community and of the region and center. The authors summarize, from the recent literature, reasons for the usual failure of SBM and identify the conditions under which SBM works, noting school and community relations and external infrastructure as important factors. The article draws strategic implications for establishing the kind of school-based developments that will positively affect learning outcomes.

Table 1. Summary of Strategic Public Relations of Teachers

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Parents	3.40	Extensive
Community	3.79	Extensive
Teaching Staff	3.32	Extensive
Staff	4.02	Extensive
Overall mean	3.63	Extensive

Table 2 shows the summary of the teachers' productivity which reveals that the overall mean is 3.31. The three indicators are presented with their corresponding mean rating namely: Physical facilities, 4.00; Grant and aids, 4.00. Two of these indicators have the descriptive equivalent of extensive. However, most of the indicators have the descriptive equivalent of less extensive.

The overall mean was 3.11 or moderately extensive which means communication, listening, teamwork, flexibility, empathy, and patience are also important attributes in a teacher. An interest in passing on knowledge, a willingness to share strategies that have worked for them, and a genuine enthusiasm for education are other important qualities in a teacher. The finding

conforms to the idea of Dirsa et al. (2022) that teachers play an essential and strategic role in education. This is because the teacher is a component of education and is at the forefront of carrying out educational goals. This educational component impacts improving the quality of teaching and students' character in schools. The teacher works directly with students to instill science and technology and instill positive values by leading and setting good examples. Teachers have a respectable position in society. Starting from his position as a teacher, he must show the correct behaviour as a teacher and make it the norm in all situations inside and outside the school according to society's expectations. Gregory et al. (2018) posited that the primary purpose of educational supervision is to improve the quality of education through teachers' efficiency and effectiveness in the discharge of classroom duties and responsibilities with the assistance of concerned administrator. Efficient and effective school leadership and teachers who could demonstrate excellent performance in the delivery of classroom instruction add up to the success of an educational agency. Ngo

et al. (2022) remarked in his study that a series of brilliant papers dealing with the human side of administration believed that the fundamental problem in all organization was in developing and maintaining dynamic and harmonious relationships. According to Mary Follet, a prominent pioneer of the new line in National Society for the study of education (1964); "it is not just a production and distribution of manufactured articles, it is also to give opportunity for individual development and self-actualization through better organization of human relationships. The process of production is as important as that of the welfare of the society as product of production". The formal work group the social environment employees has great influence on the productivity. To Mayo and others, the concept of social man (motivated by social needs, wanting-on the-job relationships and more responsive to work group pressure than to management control) has to replace the old concept of rational man motivated by personal economic needs. This theory marked the beginning of the recognition of human factor in the effectiveness of an organization.

Table 2. Summary of Strategic Public Relations of Teachers

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Parents	3.40	Extensive
Community	3.79	Extensive
Teaching Staff	3.32	Extensive
Staff	4.02	Extensive
Overall mean	3.63	Extensive

Shown in Table 3 are data about the significant relationship between teachers' public relations and productivity. Analyzing the data by Pearson Product –Moment Correlation Coefficient or Pearson r, the results are: the computed r-value for teachers' public relations versus productivity is 0.62 which denotes an almost substantial relationship or definite relationship.

While computing the significant difference of r –r-values, it is found as 4.41 with a probability value of 0.013, which is less than the 0.05 level of significance. Hence, there is a significant relationship between teachers' public relations and teachers' productivity. The greater the teachers' public relations, the greater the teachers' productivity. Hence, a positive correlation occurs

when an increase in two variables decreases at the same time. This mere example of linear correlation or straight-line relationships between two variables. A correlation can range between -1 (perfect negative relationship) and +1 (perfect positive relationship), with 0 indicating no straight-line relationship.

Table 3. Significant Relationship between Strategic Public Relations and Productivity of Teachers

Variables	r-values	Computed t-value	P value	Remarks/Decision
Public relations (x) Productivity (y)	0.62	4.41	0.013	Reject

The findings aligned with the statement of The study was anchored by Brunner (2019) Public Relations Theory explores the central principles and theoretical components of public relations and their practical applications in actual situations. This informative text helps readers to understand the concepts, approaches, and perspectives of PR theory and learn development methods, implementation strategies, management techniques, and more. Chapters written by recognized experts on each topic provide readers with knowledge on how, when, and why appropriate theories are applied. Focusing on how organizations and individuals integrate theory in a public relations framework, each chapter explains one function, explores its potential challenges and opportunities, provides an example of the function in practice, and offers discussion questions and additional reading suggestions. Unique in structure, this text arranges chapters by function, rather than theory, allowing readers to see how multiple theories can be applied to each public relations function and how theories can be used in different professional settings. Comprehensive treatment of topics including social and emerging media, globalization, public diplomacy, corporate and investor relations, and others ensures relevant and timely coverage of contemporary PR issues. As explained by Sumarsono et al. (2022) that in determining the level of ability of school ad-

ministration staff Management Archives Based on Digital Technology, and determine the differences in the ability of school administration staff in Management Archives Based on digital technology. The results of this study are: the level of School Administration Staff ability in managing archives based on digital technology is in the sufficient category, and there is a significant difference in School Administration Staff ability in Management Archives Based on digital technology. agriculture department to keep daily log of their activities for their supervisory roles, to monitor the use of time, ensuring that effective supervision does not erode. Since as more time spent in teaching is negatively related to supervision effectiveness, the Teaching Service Management in the Ministry of Education in Botswana should consider reducing the teaching time required of heads of agriculture department, so that heads of agriculture department can concentrate on supervision, and thus, improve their effectiveness. The teachers should also collaborate with the Teaching Service Management in providing an in-service training program on supervision. In-service training program should target both newly recruited heads of agriculture department and those already in the service. Osuji et al. (2022) investigated academic staff and job performance in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. The findings revealed

that there is a relationship between the availability of teaching facility, performance appraisal and job performance of teachers. Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended that adequate teaching facilities should be provided by the Rivers State Ministry of Education to aid effective teaching and learning, in order to achieve educational goals and objectives, and principals should ensure that teachers' activities and performance in the school are in congruent to educational goals, in order to upgrade teachers' performance in line with contemporary aids. Sephania et al. (2017) investigated on teachers' perception on availability of instructional materials and physical facilities in

secondary schools of Arusha district, Tanzania. The study concludes that there is an inadequate number of textbooks, reference books, maps, and globes in schools under investigation due to the increase of students in Community Schools. Further, schools have inadequate physical facilities such as classrooms, desks, and chairs, and the available classrooms are poorly constructed with inadequate spacing. Researchers recommend that Curriculum developers at Tanzania Institute of Education together with policy makers should come up with a policy guideline that will enhance provision of instructional materials and physical facilities.

Table 4. Regression Coefficient Analysis on the Influence of Strategic Public Relations and Productivity of Teachers

Model	Coefficients	Unstandardized	Standard Error	Standardized	t	p	Decision
H	(Intercept)	3.356	0.056	60.083	< .001		
H	(Intercept)	0.167	0.157	1.069	0.287		
	Parents	0.095	0.090	0.100	0.949	0.343	(Accept)
	Community	0.131	0.092	0.157	1.444	0.151	(Accept)
	Physical Facilities	0.213	0.092	0.256	2.461	0.014	(*Reject)
	Learning Environment	0.347	0.083	0.424	4.627	< .013	(*Reject)

Note: $R^2 = 0.886$, F -value = 115.460, p -value < .001

Table 12 depicts the regression coefficient analysis on the significant influence on teachers' public relations that significantly influences productivity. All indicators of teacher's strategic public relations provided, namely parents (0.343), community (0.151), physical facilities (0.014), and learning environment (0.013), are statistically significant in influencing teacher's productivity. This gives empirical evidence to show that the indicators of teacher's public relations provided directly influence teachers' productivity. Meanwhile, the R^2 value of 0.886 suggests that the teacher's public relations account 88.6 percent of the variance of the teacher's productivity. This provides empirical evidence that variability of the extent of confidence can be ac-

counted for and be explained by the indicators as enumerated under the extent of teachers' public relations in teaching. In addition, the F -value shows all the sums of squares, given regression being the model and Residual being the error. The F -value (115.460) and F -statistic are significant $p < .001$, which tells that the model is significantly a better predictor of teachers' strategic public relations in the school, and the physical facilities and learning environment significantly influence the productivity of teachers. The parent and community, with $p < 0.343$ and $p < 0.151$, mean that the probability value is less than the acceptance region with these two indicators. Therefore the null hypothesis is accepted, and therefore, these two domains of strategic

public relations do not significantly influence the productivity of teachers. Thus, teachers' public relations enabled teacher productivity in the school—strategic public relations of teachers in terms of students and learning environment. While parents and the community do not significantly influence Strategic public relations, this may be another factor that causes their less involvement or engagement in the school with the teachers. According to Bezanilla et al. (2022) how to explain principals will shape the school culture the current pressures for school reform, and the different perspectives on school operations reflected in the reform. Competing reform strategies are described, specifically, the human resources approach and the structural, political, free market, and school culture models. Aiming to link reform success to school culture and symbolic leadership concepts, the author describes organizational cultures or subcultures within the greater society and presents evidence connecting organizational culture to productivity in business and schools. The description of how the principal shapes a school culture by fulfilling five roles, the following of which are symbols, potter, poet, actor, and healer. The principals described identified what was important to the selected compatible teachers, dealt successfully with conflict, set a consistent example, told illustrative stories, and used ceremonies, traditions, rituals, and symbols to display the school's common values. It was agreed by Gre-

gory et al. (2018) that the primary purpose of educational supervision is to improve the quality of education through teachers' efficiency and effectiveness in the discharge of classroom duties and responsibilities with the assistance of the concerned administrator. Efficient and effective school leadership and teachers who could demonstrate excellent performance in the delivery of classroom instruction add up to the success of an educational agency. The findings were corroborated by the findings of Affandi et al. (2019) that the development of a model of an effective professional learning community for elementary school teachers. This research found 4 components of professional learning community, namely teacher collaboration for learning improvement, the support of resources, opportunities for collaborative learning, and the school's social capital. From the path analysis procedure, researcher found that among the 4 components of professional learning community, only teacher collaboration for learning improvement has a significant direct effect on teachers' performance. Meanwhile, the other three components have indirect effects on teachers' performance mediated by teacher collaboration for learning improvement component. For initiating professional learning community, this research suggests to put more attention to create a supportive condition for facilitating teacher collaboration for learning improvement.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

The primordial intention of this study was to establish the relationship between public relations and teacher productivity. The study subjects are the teachers of the public elementary schools of Digos City Division. The descriptive correlational were utilized. The instruments used were the survey questionnaires formulated by the researchers and evaluated by the panel

committees. Based on the analyses and interpretations of the data gathered, the following findings were drawn according to the sequence of the study's objectives. The extent of teachers' public relations with parents, community, teaching staff, and students has obtained an overall mean of 3.63 with the mean descriptive equivalent of extensive, thus oftentimes mani-

fested. The extent of teachers' productivity in terms of physical facilities, grants and aids, staff management, and learning environment was 3.11, or moderately extensive, thus sometimes manifested. There was a relationship between strategic public relations and the productivity of teachers; an R^2 value of 0.886 suggests that the teacher's public relations account for 88.6 percent of the variance of the teacher's productivity. The F-value (115.460) and F-Statistics were significant $p < .001$, which tells that the model is significantly a better predictor of teachers' public relations in the school. Results indicated that there was sufficient evidence to reject the null hypothesis. Thus, there was a significant relationship between the two variables. The parent and community, with $p < 0.343$ and $p < 0.151$, mean that the probability value is less than the acceptance region with these two indicators. Therefore the null hypothesis is accepted, and therefore, these two domains of strategic public relations do not significantly influence the productivity of teachers. Strategic public relations of teachers in terms of students, and learning environment. While parents and community do not significantly influence Strategic public relations, this may be another factor that causes their less involvement or less engagement in the school with the teachers.

4.1. Conclusions—Based on the results presented, the following conclusions were drawn: The extent of teachers' public relations with parents, community, teaching staff, and students was extensive, thus oftentimes manifested. The extent of teachers' productivity in terms of physical facilities, grants and aids, staff management, and learning environment was moderately extensive, thus sometimes manifested. There

was a relationship between strategic public relations and teacher productivity. Results indicated sufficient evidence to reject the null hypothesis. Thus, there was a significant relationship between the two variables. Two domains of strategic public relations, parent and community, do not significantly influence the productivity of teachers.

4.2. Recommendations—Based on the results of this study, the following recommendations were hereby suggested: DepEd Official may implement training and programs for teachers. The school heads must continue their initiatives on the school improvement plan (SIP) and be responsible and accountable to the school management plan (SMP), which must be specific, measurable, attainable, realistic, and time-bounded goals reflecting all the school, students, community, and all stakeholders-centered activities and programs by intensifying the public relations as to be productive as a manager of education. Teachers and School Heads. This study may provide enough information for improvement about the public relations and productivity of the teachers on the school premises and their relationship with their immediate school heads. Moreover, it would help improve the poor or gray indicators for improvement by both teachers and the support of their school heads and promote extensive indicators in the study to help them achieve more in their respective endeavors. Students. This study was beneficial for the students' information and provided knowledge on their relationship with their teachers and the school. Future researchers are hereby prompted to conduct a similar study in this regard to be conducted in the Division of Digos City.

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